

The Coupling Constants Series and the Aristocratic (3) Enigma - 8 Theory

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Abstract:

In this paper, an analysis regarding the formally majestic, in this paper Aristocratic (3). In the 8T thesis, the analysis proved it an electron. A question remain. Is there an analogous to an electron for higher term couplings? In other words, is this the electron in each of the coupling series terms? In the 8T thesis, one regarded the (3) to be different in each coupling terms. However, it is now vivid that it could be just the electron for any additional higher terms.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \rightarrow \frac{3^2}{128} \quad (2.12)$$

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1) \quad (3.0)$$

$$\frac{3^2}{128} = \frac{8 + (1)}{128} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\frac{8 + (1)}{128} \rightarrow \frac{(1)}{128} = \frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \quad (3.2)$$

That was the construction used to prove that the aristocratic (3) is the electron. In the 8T thesis, we also used the second representation, i.e. spin representation.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.3)$$

The 8T thesis did not put any kind attention to this very important question and assumed that for each term there would be an analogous element, which is the destabilizer factor of the coupling term. However, here in this paper, a second option, which we presented above, is manifested itself. That for all terms it is the strong interaction boson emitted and there are no analogous element for each higher term of the series.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

So for each term in the coupling from the second and above it is the electron, and there is no analogue in higher terms. Such an option than is immense simplification in terms of the final theory as there are infinitely many couplings terms, isomorphic to $\mathbb{P} \oplus (+1)$. Therefore, we can cut the number of elements participating in one-half, if all the destabilizing factors converge to a single entity, i.e. the electron. As one is no particle physicist, such an option did not accrue beforehand in construction of the coupling constant series and he regarded each term to be distinct. Than the proof made in equations (2.11) to (3.2) would satisfy and apply to each higher term of the coupling, not just to the coupling of the electric.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)